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Table of Contents

Executive summary	3
1 Introduction	4
1.1 Purpose	4
1.2 Contributions of partners.....	4
1.3 Report structure	4
2 The role of PAMs in BEMServer	5
2.1 The BEMServer platform	5
2.2 Prototype PAMs.....	6
2.3 Module refinements	9
2.4 Module testing	10
3 Lessons learned from trial deployments.....	13
3.1 For facility managers.....	13
3.2 For future BEMServer development.....	14
3.3 For those deploying simulation modules of BEMServer	15
3.4 For developers of design and simulation tools	16
4 Conclusions.....	17
5 References.....	18
6 Acronyms and abbreviations	19

Executive summary

This report summarises the potential benefits delivered to large estate facility managers by the performance assessment modules (PAMs) developed within the EC HIT2Gap project. During the project, PAMs were integrated with a new data platform, BEMServer, for use to reduce the performance gap between intent and actualisation in relation to energy use, occupant well-being and systems control in commercial buildings. Specifically, this report describes the deployed PAMs, which cover a range of operational issues, and their refinements as required over the course of the project in response to trial applications to real buildings. The report also summarises the overall lessons learned as a contribution to future PAM development and application by facility managers (FM) wishing to employ such tools to address the operational issues that contribute to the performance gap.

The BEMServer platform allows (among other capabilities) FMs to commission comprehensive performance assessments without the need to recreate input models, coordinate performance assessments, extract results or even acquire a software licence. Instead, and in response to observed issues (such as high energy use or overheating complaints), they are able to invoke assessments as a means to inform and compare possible remedial actions.

The work undertaken by the HIT2Gap consortium to date has created a novel data platform that supports the diverse requirements of different performance domain assessments and provides a framework for tool developers aiming to add new functionality in future – as required by particular estates, local legislation or different application sectors such as industry and agriculture.

Based on experiences derived from trials of the BEMServer approach by FMs responsible for 3 large estates, various lessons were learned and are reported here. These lessons, which relate to both the application and future refinement of BEMServer PAMs, include:

the ability to:

- map actual performance and update predictions;
- explore scenarios to mitigate performance problems;
- investigate conflicting performance goals; and
- identify faulty or misconfigured components (where simulation represent the ideal state).

and the need for:

- criteria for assessment invocation;
- automation for predictive actions, exploratory studies and trade-off evaluations;
- closer integration of the modules,
- improvements in the consistency of user interfaces; and
- better understanding of principal model parameters to support model calibration.

While such lessons are focused on building operation, they can also be used to guide improvements to design tools in order that they are better able to tackle the operational issues encountered in real buildings (and observed during BEMServer development).

The integration of BEMServer into the facilities management workflow, and the new skills required by FMs for its effective utilisation, are challenges to be faced during the dissemination and exploitation of the HIT2Gap project outcomes. As a proof of concept, the project has delivered a novel contribution that enables the routine use of performance simulation to support building operation. The lessons learned can be used to guide both the future refinement of existing modules and the development of new ones.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This report summarises the benefits delivered to large estate facility managers by the performance assessment modules (PAMs) of the BEMServer approach. Specifically, it describes the PAMs as deployed, the refinements to these modules over the course of the project, and the lessons learned from trial applications to real buildings. The outcome is a demonstration of the new functionality available to FMs wishing to address the operational issues that contribute to the performance gap. Lessons learned during the deployment of the PAMs are summarised from FM, BEMServer developer and design tool developer viewpoints.

This report is the product of task 5.5, which considered the benefits brought by the HIT2Gap approach in the field of design and simulation tools. While the tests conducted at the pilot sites demonstrated benefits related to the operational phase, they also gave insight into the need to refine tools for application at the design stage. Such refinements will include, for example, emulation of building commissioning and operation, and the continuing evolution of the building model post-occupancy.

1.2 Contributions of partners

UOS, as the leader of task 5.5 and responsible for deliverable D5.4, is the main contributor to this document. Other partners involved in the task 5.5 activities (CYR, FISE, NUIG, ZUT) have contributed by providing descriptions of the role, refinements and testing of their module and a summary of the lessons they learned in the process.

1.3 Report structure

The following section summarises the assessment modules, how they are connected to the BEMServer platform, how they were deployed within the pilot buildings and the refinements that were implemented after FM testing. The following section then summarises the lessons learned from the module configuration and application activities, and the relevance of these to three target groups: FMs, developers of the core BEMServer platform, and developers of future PAMs.

2 The role of PAMs in BEMServer

2.1 The BEMServer platform

The HIT2Gap project developed a data-centred solution aiming to bring timely support to the facility management process and thereby help reduce the energy performance gap [1]. The BEMServer platform that has been established to deliver this solution comprises four operational levels as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: BEMServer architecture.

From bottom up, these levels relate to 1) connecting the platform to field measuring devices, 2) performing basic data manipulations to ensure quality, 3) storing the measured data at the required temporal frequencies, and 4) providing specific data collections to user-oriented applications addressing particular aspects of building performance such as energy use reduction, indoor environmental quality improvement, HVAC system control adaptation, local renewable energy systems deployment and the like. The platform essentially allows data collected from a variety of sources, and at any required frequency, to be made available from a central source to support the invocation of each PAM. The data at the third level are structured via a semantic model developed within the project to meet the needs of building operations appraisal. The open nature of the platform enables future module developers to exploit data availability (after obtaining access permission), propose additional field measurements and connect new applications as required.

2.2 Prototype PAMs

A representative range of prototype PAMs were developed by the project partners corresponding to data visualisation, fault detection, energy use forecasting, user behaviour, energy management and operational performance assessment. The last module type is the subject of this report, while details on the other modules are available elsewhere [2-4]. PAMs are intended to provide insights that cannot be obtained via monitored data manipulation alone, i.e. they provide a performance simulation capability that may be used to compare and contrast counter-factual cases. While the potential of computer-based performance assessment is vast, the capability of the applications deployed within the BEMServer prototype are restricted to principal topics only: energy use and supply; HVAC systems performance; indoor environmental quality; control system tuning; and the visualisation of model and performance data. These developments correspond to a proof of concept effort and it may be expected that the tools connected in future will be both widened in scope and deepened in rigour in response to evolving needs.

Table 1 lists the 4 PAMs connected to the BEMServer prototype, their respective scope, the performance assessments delivered and the pilot sites used for testing. The test buildings, which were located in France, Spain and the Republic of Ireland, are described in detail elsewhere [6].

Table 1: BEMServer applications and functionality.

Application	Scope	Performance assessments	Tested on
ESP-r (UOS)	Identification of the location and cause of inappropriate indoor environmental conditions.	Spatial distribution of thermal comfort. Façade discomfort glare and daylight utilisation. Indoor air quality.	Challenger (BES) Alice Perry building (NUIG)
REnSIM (CYR)	Identification of PV system performance degradation.	Derating factor modelling of dust, snow, aging effects and other parameters that affect PV performance.	Challenger (BES)
ModSCO (NUIG)	Assessment of HVAC operation strategies to improve performance while maintaining Service Level Constraints.	Off-line performance assessment of control strategies.	Alice Perry building (NUIG)
GapReasoner (FISE)	Performance gap analysis.	Uncertainty/ sensitivity analysis coupled with fault detection and diagnostics.	Nanogune (GIR)

It should be noted that the scopes identified in Table 1 were selected to demonstrate a range of performance assessment capability and do not imply that a particular module is limited to that scope; as and when required, additional assessment capability can be enabled and/ or a new PAM added to the platform.

The specific modules included in the BEMServer prototype include: ModSCO [5] developed by the National University of Ireland Galway and concerned with HVAC systems control, GapReasoner developed by Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems and concerned with identifying the cause of a departure from expected performance, ESP-r [7] developed by the Energy Systems

Research Unit (ESRU) at the University of Strathclyde (with contributions from many others) and concerned with indoor environmental conditions (thermal, visual and air quality), and REnSIM developed by Cyric and concerned with solar thermal/ electrical energy systems. Two support modules were also developed to assist with performance assessment interpretation: a visualisation tool developed by ZUTEC for model visualisation with performance outcomes superimposed; and Calibro [8] developed by ESRU for automated input model calibration using performance data retrieved from the platform.

These modules may be obtained from the following locations under the indicated terms.

- ModSCO – Free to use, available from <https://www.modsco.ie>.
- GapReasoner – Proprietary, licence information on request from Fraunhofer ISE;
- ESP-r – Open Source, free to use, available from <https://www.strath.ac.uk/research/energysystemsresearchunit/applications/>;
- REnSIM – Proprietary, licence information on request from www.cyric.eu;
- ZUTEC tool – Proprietary, licence information on request from www.zutec.com.

The implementation of the PAMs listed in Table 1 required tool developments, customisations and refinements to meet the project requirements. The new features required by all modules included:

- functions to transact with the platform to retrieve data and return performance assessment outcomes;
- a Web interface to facilitate FM appraisal requests and access to outcomes;
- functions to fetch and automatically calibrate the related input model prior to use; and
- the ability to impose performance predictions on 3D model images.

These developments have imparted a plug & play capability to the modules, facilitating their future deployment within other estates in future.

Interactions with the platform require a digital certificate issued by the platform and are implemented via a RESTful API developed by the HIT2Gap lead partner, NOBATEK [9]. Since this form of interaction with data storage is not typical within performance assessment tools, it required developments that shift the focus from a standalone desktop application to a Web service deployed in a secure cloud server. Some deployed modules embrace this new architecture by providing a Web interface based on an iframe solution provided by NOBATEK and, in some cases, an API to enable direct inter-program communication in future.

As an example, Figure 2 depicts the platform transactions implemented for the ESP-r module, while Figure 3 shows examples of the Web interfaces developed for the ESP-r and ModSCO modules. In the case of ESP-r, and following an assessment request via the interface, all platform interactions and the simulation process itself are automated. The former comprise actions related to (pre-constructed) input model fetching, (automated) model calibration, monitored data fetching (e.g. performance data for calibration and weather data for simulation boundary conditions definition), and performance returns. The latter comprise pre-defined program control scripts corresponding to standard performance appraisals as described below.

Figure 2: ESP-r BEMServer transactions.

Figure 3: ESP-r and ModSCO cloud server interfaces.

Performance assessment processes require two additional functionalities that can be seen as external to the performance assessment module itself, namely model calibration and visualisation.

Model calibration

Model calibration is an essential step prior to commissioning a performance assessment and, since BEMServer is intended for deployment in existing estates, real performance data is always available to enable the action. (This is not meant to imply that obtaining these data is a non-trivial task). This leads to the situation whereby input models are automatically recalibrated prior to use. This contributes to a narrowing of the performance gap by permitting the replacement of design stage assumptions with operational stage observations.

Traditionally, model calibration has been undertaken as an *ad hoc* activity performed by an experienced modeller. The Calibro module is an automated procedure that is tool agnostic, i.e. it will operate with any PAM independent of its underlying theory and assumptions. The procedure requires

input-output datasets corresponding to several runs of a module. These data are then subjected to statistical tests resulting in modified input parameter values that ensure agreement between the simulated and observed performance.

Visualisation

Another feature required by all modules is the visualisation of performance data. As BEMServer intends to bring simulation capabilities to FMs who are non-experts in simulation, the ability to display results in an intuitive manner is required. To this end, Zutec connected a BIM model visualisation tool to the platform and enabled the superimposition of performance returns from the PAMs listed in Table 1. Again, this solution is tool agnostic in that any information can be displayed as long as it is accompanied by attributes that allow a mapping to a related location and time.

These common functionalities required customised new features within each module as summarised in the following section.

2.3 Module refinements

ModSCO utilises the R-C network method based on previous work by Bacher and Madsen [10]. The algorithms are implemented using the Modelica programming language in conjunction with the Modelica Standard Library [11] and the Modelica Buildings Library [12]. The main development in the project was to establish a reduced order model that can be variously instanced by a user, sent for simulation and have the results visualised. The core model sits statically in the application as a Functional Mock-Up Unit (FMU) file. This contains the equations, libraries and solvers to run the model so no critical dependencies or external firmware needs to be accessed. The model contained in it is called using a long open-source stack (PyFMI and dependencies) and integrated in the server side of ModSCO. The web interface to data, variables, parameter sets, results and BEMServer integration was developed using Django MVC framework. A full account of ModSCO's functionality is given elsewhere [3]. The main developments undertaken within the project and tested in the Alice Perry Engineering Building included establishing a forms-based approach to model definition and administration, developing a module for the retrieval and the visualisation of results (time-series), integrating the app with BEMServer for standalone use, and enabling cooperation with other BEMServer modules for model calibration [8,13], Fault Detection & Diagnosis - Principal Component Analysis (FDD-PCA) and Energy Management (ENERIT).

GapReasoner is a module based on uncertainty analysis (UA) and sensitivity analysis (SA) applied to building performance simulation. The module runs simulation models with a set of uncertain input parameters imposed relating to building configuration, weather conditions, occupancy *etc.* The simulation results (e.g. energy consumption) are represented by probability distributions according to the input probability distributions of the uncertain parameters. Major influences on the energy consumption are then listed as a means to provide FMs with an insight into cost-effective energy efficiency improvements. Prior to the HIT2Gap project, the UA/ SA software solution at FISE was a prototype, which was converted to a functional module of the platform. The work required included: re-writing the code in a high-level language; connecting the module using the FMI standard for communication with simulation components available in Modelica libraries; adopting the monitoring and data analysis platform mondas[®] to provide pre-processed, persistently stored input data; and implementing communication protocols with the platform. A provisional interface implementation for configuration of the routine was developed as well as dashboards for examining the simulation results.

ESP-r is a multi-physics energy system modelling environment enabling the simulation of heat, mass and momentum exchanges within and between the building fabric, indoor spaces, HVAC systems and renewable energy components [14]. Within the project, ESP-r was adapted to allow the importing of BIM models in the gbXML format and to provide indoor environmental quality assessments based

on international and European standards for thermal comfort [15], visual comfort [16] and air quality [17]. These assessments are automated and do not require any user input apart from the selection of the assessment type and the period to be considered. Upon request, ESP-r retrieves a pre-constructed building model – as developed by the FM team or commissioned from an external organisation – from the BEMServer platform along with weather and performance data, the latter to enable automated model calibration via the Calibro module. The requested assessment, which is undertaken on a virtual server, produces three outputs: a concise report on the assessment outcome in terms of key performance metrics; a file with the same metrics structured in machine readable JSON format for direct access by other platform modules; and a database containing the simulation results for the processed model for deeper enquiry. These outputs can be accessed via the BEMServer platform where each assessment is stored using the event data structure of the API.

REnSIM is the result of improvements to a pre-existing tool. This PAM is intended as a decision support tool for the design of new, or retrofitting of existing, renewable energy infrastructure. Within the project, the module was extended to support the design, optimal sizing and real-time calculation of energy output from photovoltaic and solar water heating systems. The module was configured to retrieve weather and energy data from BEMServer for use in an algorithm that attempts to minimise the difference between the expected and actual energy production of renewable energy systems. A range of graphic outputs was implemented to facilitate analysis by FMs. The solution was developed using MongoDB for the database for scalability and a dedicated API was developed.

2.4 Module testing

Because PAM validity is the subject of completed and ongoing work conducted elsewhere, only a limited effort was expended within HIT2Gap in this regard (although it should be noted that all models are calibrated using monitored data prior to use, thus ensuring their validity across a narrow range). Instead, the applicability of PAMs to FM need was tested through deployment in one or more HIT2Gap pilot sites. The selection of sites for each module was based on site features, information availability and site complexity. The applicability of REnSIM, for example, could only be tested at sites with solar energy resources such as the Challenger estate. ModSCO was tested at the Alice Perry Engineering Building as the control of HVAC systems was a particular issue of concern to the resident FM. The choice of the Challenger and NUIG sites for ESP-r testing was based on the availability of detailed information as required to construct the necessary high-resolution models to enable IEQ assessment. GapReasoner was tested at the nanoGUNE building, due to the complexity of this building and its HVAC systems which make identifying the reasons for the gap particularly challenging.

For each pilot site and PAM combination, fit-for-purpose models of the building and systems were prepared as required. Prerequisites for the development of such models includes access to building and systems specifications, availability of measured performance data and a BMS that supports interoperability with other applications. Figure 4 shows a high-resolution model as established for the South Triangle building within the Challenger estate as required to enable detailed IEQ simulations.

Figure 4: Example of a simulation model for a portion of the Challenger building for IEQ assessments by ESP-r.

The complexity of these models varies between PAMs, with some requiring information about particular energy systems, some requiring information about the building only, and some requiring information about both building and system. In most cases, the establishment of a model is a non-trivial exercise requiring the collation of information from disparate and uncertain sources such as design stage models, architectural/ engineering drawings, site visits *etc.* That said, the model, once created, can be reused with only minor updates to reflect building alterations. In the present context, the model development work was carried out by the related PAM developer assisted by the local FM team. In the future, the evolution of BIM standards may facilitate the direct transfer of BIM models from design phase to the operation activities.

The tests took place over the winter period 2018-9 and comprised several scenarios for each site as suggested by the FMs (a detailed list is given elsewhere [18]). During the tests, each PAM was invoked by the local FM team with feedback elicited to guide module improvement.

Figure 5 presents an example of an assessment outcome as produced for a set of workstations at the Challenger pilot site. This figure shows photorealistic views indicating (by red circles) areas with high luminance (in cd/m^2). Comparing the simulated values with relevant standards allowed the FM

to identify workstations with high glare risk and thereby implement preventive measures, such as layout modifications or changes in automated blinds set-points. The outcomes of these assessments were compared with conditions encountered in the test building as a means to evaluate the applicability of the simulation-based approach in a facilities management context. The application of ESP-r within the Alice Perry Engineering Building, for example, indicated excessive overheating, the cause of which was eventually traced to a malfunctioning space temperature controller. It also highlighted the need to replace the international standard for thermal comfort evaluation by a more suitable local standard (a feature was subsequently implemented to support the use of other standards identified by the FM). ModSCo was also used to test the impact of altering temperature set-points (heating and cooling) on energy use with the outcome used to select the most beneficial strategy.

The development of performance assessment modules and their deployment and testing at the pilot sites gave rise to several insights that may be useful for BEMServer module users and developers as discussed in the next section.

Figure 5: Examples of visual comfort assessment results.

3 Lessons learned from trial deployments

3.1 For facility managers

The following eight paragraphs summarise the principal lessons that are relevant within this category.

A core causal element of the performance gap is the separation in time between predictions (carried out in the design phase and under a variety of assumptions) and performance monitoring (carried out under actual operating conditions). By providing calibrated models and simulation capabilities for FMs, BEMServer provides a means to explore the factors that contribute to the performance gap at the building operation stage. Comparisons between calibrated model outputs and actual performance can be used to study causality and thereby change aspects such as building operation and use, or system configuration and control. The process can also assist with the identification of reasons for system malfunction. In one trial (Alice Perry Building), for example, simulation predictions were at odds with observations and on investigation, a pernicious control system malfunction was discovered that had remained undetected for several years and caused severe overheating.

Because experimentation cannot be carried out on an actual building, performance impacts may be studied by applying simulation under various scenarios. This capability is a valuable addition to the FM's toolbox. The use of REnSIM at the Challenger building, for example, led to the identification of a performance issue with the PV system, which was then rectified by the FM. The ESP-r module when deployed at the Alice Perry Building helped identify problems with the HVAC control system configuration. Possible changes to the control parameters were then investigated using ModSCO. Such analyses, leading to performance improvement, would not be feasible without recourse to the functionality provided by the BEMServer PAMs.

The possibility to compare the impact on energy use, HVAC system configuration *etc.* given real occupant behaviour as opposed to design stage assumptions that may be a poor representation of the reality, proved to be an effective way to address the performance gap. As an example, one model calibration resulted in recommended parameter values that implied an occupancy behaviour that was significantly at odds with that assumed at the design stage, the outcome from which informed the control settings imposed at the building commissioning stage.

PAMs also support FM activities relating to the ongoing commissioning of the building and systems. Commissioning assures the building is performing as expected and one of the reason for the performance gap is the lack of continuation of this process post occupancy. By carrying out frequent performance assessments, it is possible to continually compare actual performance with the ideal state and make adjustments that avoid the appearance of a performance gap in the first place.

The deployment of BEMServer within an estate will likely require changes to the work practices of FMs. In the short term, minor changes might suffice, requiring the regular initiation of assessments and the analysis of outcomes. In the longer term, FMs may be expected to undertake new tasks such as: the deployment of energy sub-metering and environmental monitoring devices; the development of building model variants to support energy action planning; attending to data quality assurance; and acquiring time synchronised weather data. Such work practices are likely to require a change in the composition of FM teams, possibly requiring the retraining of staff and/ or the creation of a dedicated position to manage BEMServer in the case of large estates.

BEMServer performance assessments provide a comprehensive view of conflicting targets to be met by FMs. By providing energy and thermal comfort assessments, for example, BEMServer can be used by FMs to investigate trade-offs in changing system HVAC set-points, which may improve thermal comfort but at the expense of an increase in energy consumption. As another example, Figure 5 shows example outputs for visual comfort, which can be used to evaluate the trade-offs in the control of shading devices (energy performance benefit of higher solar gains in the winter versus an increase in the probability of glare). These capabilities support a more holistic approach to decision-making by FMs, as traditionally changes in building operation are carried out without further evaluation of their impacts on other areas of the building.

The connectivity capabilities of BMS applications should be scrutinised by FM in order to support the deployment of BEMServer. Performance data is a central element of the assessments described in this report, and the project demonstrated the variable degree of difficulties when connecting the existing data infrastructure of a building (mainly the BMS) with an external application (here BEMServer). Buildings that have open protocols in place and direct access to monitoring results databases were able to implement BEMServer faster and at a lower cost than those relying on proprietary closed systems. In the second group, the deployment of BEMServer required significant changes in the existing infra-structure and this will hinder the adoption of BEMServer in future.

Making trade-offs between different performance aspects is a challenging problem for FMs. The use of PAMs prompt questions about the gain, for example, in thermal comfort against additional energy use and the cost of deploying BEMServer itself. This multi-criteria problem requires new skills from FMs and also knowledge in performance standards addressing various aspects of building operation. The project identified the need for the continuing professional development of FMs targeting such issues. Only then will FMs be able to exploit the full capabilities of the PAMs provided by BEMServer. This will also facilitate the deployment of BEMServer, as FMs will be aware of its benefits, reducing resistance to the introduction of the platform.

3.2 For future BEMServer development

The following five paragraphs summarise the principal lessons that are relevant within this category.

Weather data is an input used by all simulation modules and BEMServer can benefit from additional developments in this regard. The current solution is semi-robust as it fills missing data (either in time or by parameter) with data fetched via dedicated APIs connected to national weather centres. This solution would be refined by using BEMServer's capability to collect data from a local weather station (an option that was not available at any of the pilot sites). At present, each PAM is required to compose its required weather collection via multiple transactions with the platform corresponding to the parameters required and its time duration. The preconstruction of weather collections would increase the efficiency of the platform transactions and avoid the present repetition brought about by each module initiating its own fetching and post-processing operations.

At present, the invocation of performance assessments requires user action. New functionality is needed to automate the process by invoking relevant assessments in response to trigger events. For example, the assessment of renewable energy generation might be triggered if yield falls below a given threshold with the result, where the magnitude of the departure from some ideal state is high, used to invoke an action. Another example is the automation of daily IEQ assessments with the results used to alert FMs, enabling them to anticipate occupant complaints and fast track responsive action. In more critical cases, more urgent alerts (or alarms) can be automatically issued based on PAM outcomes. It is envisaged that new BEMServer modules will be added in future that utilise existing assessments in an Artificial Intelligence environment that aims to better support the facilities management process.

The treatment of conflicts between different performance criteria could also be addressed in future by providing a feature that is able to search for acceptable trade-offs based on the returns from several performance assessments undertaken by one or more PAMs. Such an automation of module invocation may also be extended to include background explorations of building/ system refurbishments as part of planned upgrades to be rolled out over time.

As an interim measure, module outcomes can be integrated by conflating all assessment returns on a common dashboard allowing FMs to scrutinise multi-variate performance and action responses as required. Such a capability could be rapidly prototyped by utilising the 3D BIM visualisation tool from Zutec, the BMS system interaction tool from Cylon and/ or the energy management tool from Enerit. The dedicated APIs offered by some PAMs (e.g. REnSIM and ESP-r) would allow these tools to request assessments without any user intervention. Similar API's should be mandated for all connected assessment modules.

BEMServer will benefit from guidelines and tools intended to provide a more coherent user experience. During the HIT2Gap project, each module developer had complete freedom to design a Web user-interface and this has resulted in a plethora of approaches. The deployment and testing within the pilot buildings highlighted issues in the approach taken by each module and this feedback should be utilised to harmonise future implementations. The development of consistent interfaces can be supported by a BEMServer software development kit (SDK). SDKs are used in the industry to facilitate the work of new developers by providing tools to tackle the most common tasks encountered in given applications. During the project, NOBATEK took this role by sharing sample code for several recurrent tasks relating to platform interaction. The experience gained can be harnessed to provide a BEMServer-specific SDK to reduce software development costs and provide better operational efficiency.

3.3 For those deploying simulation modules of BEMServer

The following seven paragraphs summarise the key lessons that are relevant within this category.

The deployment of BEMServer in a building is a non-trivial task. To support the simulation-based modules, several actions are required to initially configure BEMServer:

- information collection regarding the building, its systems and operation;
- definition of areas of the building and sub-systems to be included in the model;
- building survey to produce as-built documentation;
- development and testing of the simulation model for the particular application;
- identification of sensors in the modelled area;
- connection of sensors with BEMServer to retrieve data; and
- data organisation regarding weather and performance for the modelled area.

In addition, arrangements must be made to support:

- model calibration using weather and performance data;
- comparisons between measured and predicted performance data to quantify the performance gap; and
- the return of the calibrated models and performance assessment outcomes to the platform.

Regarding information gathering, it was noticeable that only one of the pilot sites (Challenger) had results of energy performance modelling produced during the design phase; even then the model was unavailable. As a consequence, no model from the design phase was reused in the project. The availability of such models and their reuse in future would significantly streamline the initial

BEMServer configuration. The maintenance of PAM-specific building models over the life-cycle of the building is an important contribution of the HIT2Gap project, as all models are known to the platform and may be accessed by authenticated individuals and/ or PAMs as and when required.

BIM remains limited in relation to the requirements of building performance simulation and so only partial BIM exchanges were possible within the BEMServer prototype. In one case (the NUIG pilot site), a model addressing the building shell was available as an IFC schema equivalent to BIM level 2. No pilot site had a BIM model addressing HVAC, controls or renewable energy systems. The anticipated access to higher level BIM models in future will bring about efficiency gains in relation to model sharing and pave the way for a greater degree of interaction between the PAMs connected to the platform. This new capability will be of interest to building owner, constructors and operators.

The construction of PAM input models requires extensive information about the building, and gathering this information proved to be a time-consuming task. The documentation made available by pilot site partners was fragmented, incomplete and lacked structure, as often seen in the building industry. The documentation from pilot sites did not include soft-landing documentation, and in many cases, there were discrepancies between the available documentation and the building. The existence of as-built documentation would greatly facilitate the initial establishment of high-resolution models as a prerequisite of digital support for future facilities management.

While the availability of an automated calibration module within BEMServer is a significant advance, it introduces new challenges. Model calibration requires deep understanding of the parameters to be calibrated for a given model. This requires model developers to formally identify the parameters requiring calibration, with likely inputs from FMs in relation to principal sources of uncertainty within the operational building.

The experience from the pilot site trials indicated potential for improvement in the commissioning process in cases where the BEMServer modules identified building features that were not installed or configured in accordance with design specifications. In most pilot sites, there was no clear understanding of the magnitude of the performance gap prior to the HIT2Gap project. This is related to the absence of a structured approach towards energy management, as prescribed, for example, by ISO 50001 [19]. The integration of energy management elements at the design stage could be facilitated by simulation tools if consideration of relevant KPIs were added.

3.4 For developers of design and simulation tools

In the context of HIT2Gap, building performance simulation tools have to be adapted to a cloud server environment. For instance, configuration of model parameters has to be made possible through a Web interface, input data has to be accessed through a Web API and outputs have to be made available for download. This way of structuring performance simulation software will be of interest to the developers of simulation tools. In HIT2Gap at present, each PAM requires its own input model and access interface. The adoption of a common interface approach – such as FMU/ FMI for example – would streamline the connection of multiple PAMs with the time series data stored on BEMServer and thereby enable application extension. There is also an urgent need to evolve the BIM standard to accommodate the non-trivial needs of PAMs addressing assessments involving many interacting technical domains.

4 Conclusions

This report gave an overview of the role of performance assessment modules in the HIT2Gap project and the lessons learned during the development, deployment and testing of these modules when applied to real buildings. Specifically, the project explored the usefulness of performance simulation for FMs, providing information about several aspects of the performance gap.

Key lessons for FMs comprise the ability to:

- map actual performance and update predictions;
- explore scenarios to mitigate performance problems;
- investigate conflicting performance goals; and
- identify faulty or misconfigured components (where simulation results are considered to represent the ideal state).

The integration of BEMServer into the facilities management workflow and the new skills required by FMs for its operation are challenges to be faced during the dissemination and exploitation of the HIT2Gap project outcomes.

Key lessons for future BEMServer development include several needs:

- criteria for assessment invocation;
- automation for predictive actions, exploratory studies and trade-off evaluations;
- closer integration of the modules,
- improvements in the consistency of user interfaces; and
- better understanding of principal model parameters to support model calibration.

As a proof of concept, the HIT2Gap project has delivered a novel contribution that enables the routine use of performance simulation to address building operational problems and opportunities. The lessons learned can be used to guide the future refinement of existing modules and the development of new ones.

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6 Acronyms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BES	Bouygues Energies et Services
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CYR	CYRIC
EUR	EURECAT
FISE	Fraunhofer ISE
FM	Facility Manager
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
GIR	GIROA
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, Air Conditioning
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
NUIG	National University of Ireland Galway
PAM	Performance Assessment Module
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SA	Sensitivity Analysis
SDK	Software Development Kit
UA	Uncertainty Analysis
UOS	University of Strathclyde
ZUT	ZUTEC